

Solvent Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Niobium and Tantalum-Quinizarin-3-Sulphonic Acid Complexes with Benzylamine, Dodecylamine and Tridecylamine in Benzene

R. M. AWADALLAH

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Aswan, Assiut University, A. R. Egypt

Manuscript received 16 March 1979, accepted 30 November 1979

The study of the extraction of Nb^{5+} - or Ta^{5+} - QuS complex between benzylamine, dodecylamine or tridecylamine (in benzene) and aqueous solutions at pH 10.5 and 9 for Nb^{5+} and Ta^{5+} , respectively. The stepwise and overall extraction efficiency and distribution coefficient were calculated, after different time intervals and equilibration.

NIObIUM and tantalum can be separated from each other and from accompanying elements, by liquid-liquid extraction of their complexes. The use of solvent extraction as a general method of separation in analytical chemistry has increased markedly in recent years as a powerful separation technique.

Benzylamine, dodecylamine and tridecylamine are liquid anion (baes) exchangers of high molecular weight amines (electrolytes), proving useful in chemical processing of extraction due to their ionic functional groups.

Niobium and or tantalum complexes with catechol^{1,2}, pyrogallol³, dithiocarbamate derivatives^{4,5,6} and 1, 2, 3, triphenylguanidine⁷ can be extracted from weakly acid solutions employing *n*-butanol, ethyl acetate, chloroform and nitrobenzene as extractants.

Experimental

Solutions :

$5 \times 10^{-3} M$ - Nb^{5+} or Ta^{5+} was prepared by fusing the appropriate amount of Nb_2O_5 or Ta_2O_5 (A.R., 99.9%) with $K_2S_2O_7$ (A.R.). The melt was dissolved in 20% tartaric acid solution⁸.

$1 \times 10^{-2} M$ -quinizarin-3-sulphonic acid solution was prepared by dissolving the required quantity of the dye in bidistilled water⁹.

Boric, succinic, sodium sulphate, borax and sodium carbonate buffers of pH's 9 and 10.5, were prepared according to Thiel, Shulz and Coch¹⁰.

Working Procedure :

The Nb^{5+} - and Ta^{5+} -QuS complexes ($[Nb^{5+}] = [Ta^{5+}] = 3 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[QuS] = 3 \times 10^{-4} M$) were prepared

from buffer solutions of pH 10.5 and 9, and waiting for 40 and 30 min for maximum colour development of Nb^{5+} and Ta^{5+} , respectively^{11,12}. Equal volumes of the complex and organic solvent (10 ml) were shaken together (using 60 ml separatory funnel) for a certain time. The phases separated were subjected to spectrophotometric measurements (using spectronic 20 spectrophotometer, 1.16 cm light path, Silica cell, Bausch & Lomb) for the study of the effect of solvent on λ_{max} , and on the absorption spectra of the complex. The effect of time of shaking on extraction efficiency was also studied. Multiple stage extraction was also performed, using small aliquots of the organic solvent (3, 4 and 3 mls) instead of the whole quantity at one time. In all cases, a blank solution containing the same concentration of ligand was used to compensate the absorbance due to ligand.

Calibration Graph :

For preparing the standard curve of Nb^{5+} -QuS complex, an aliquot of buffer solution of pH 10.5 was shaken with equal volume of organic solvent (benzylamine, dodecylamine and tridecylamine in benzene) for 1,5,6 and 7 minutes, whereas in case of Ta^{5+} -QuS complex, equal volumes of buffer solution of pH 9 and organic solvent (benzylamine, dodecylamine and tridecylamine) were shaken together for 1, 5 and 6 minutes. The aqueous phases saturated with these organic solvents were used in the preparation of the standard series of solutions of Nb^{5+} or Ta^{5+} -QuS using constant concentration of quinizarin and variable concentrations of Nb^{5+} or Ta^{5+} ranging from $1 - 5 \times 10^{-5} M$.

Results and Discussion

When Nb^{5+} -QuS solution is shaken with benzylamine and tridecylamine, λ_{max} (460 nm) is not affected, whereas that of Nb^{5+} -QuS with

dodecylamine is shifted to $\lambda=440$ nm (hypsochromic shift) due to the effect of solvent on λ_{\max} . The Nb⁵⁺-QuS complex in the dodecylamine layer gives maximum at $\lambda=520$. The results obtained are recorded in Tables 1, 2 and 3. The data reveal that the extraction efficiency and hence, distribution coefficient in case of tantalum are higher than that of niobium due to that the effective nuclear charge of tantalum is less than that of niobium and hence the acidity of tantalum is higher than that of niobium. Generally speaking, the percentage of extraction increases from benzylamine to dodecylamine due to that the electron density on the nitrogen atom of the amino group in dodecylamine (secondary aliphatic amine) is less than that of benzylamine (Primary aromatic amine) which proves well to attach to the central metal ion of Nb⁵⁺- or Ta⁵⁺-QuS complex through hydrogen bonding to take up all the complex into the organic phase (The solvent molecule participate directly in the formation of ion association complexes). The complete extraction with dodecyl amine may be also due to the sufficiently high dielectric constant that ions can exist in them, and their electron donor properties allow metal cations to be stabilised by solvation.

It is well established that dodecylamine is a powerful extractant than benzylamine and tridecylamine. Dodecylamine justifies all the requirements needed for a good extractant.

The lower values of the percentage of extraction and distribution coefficient of niobium and tantalum on using tridecylamine as extractant may be due to

the effect of the steric hinderance of the methyl groups of the tertiary amine (tertiary branched chain amine), which may break the hydrogen bond established between the extractant and the complex compound.

References

1. F. V. ZAIKOVSKII, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1956, **11**, 269.
2. F. V. ZAIKOVSKII, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1956, **11**, 553.
3. J. A. CATOGGIO and L. B. ROGERS, *Talanta*, 1962, **9**, 377.
4. H. A. TYATINA, V. B. ALESKOVSKII and A. D. MILLER, *Trudy leniger. Tekhnol. Inst. in. Lensoveta* 48, 101 1958, Ref. *Zhur. Khim.*, 1959, 11, Abstr. No. 38, 317.
5. I. M. GIBALO, I. P. ALIMARIN and P. DAVAADORZH, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. SSSR*, 1963, **149**, 1326.
6. I. M. GIBALO, I. P. ALIMARIN and P. DAVAADORZH, *Zhur. Anal. Khim.*, 1964, **19**, 467 ; 1963, **18**, 835 ; *Vesta. Mask gas, Univ. Ser. Khim.*, 1965, **4**, 73.
7. I. P. ALIMARIN and O. M. PETRUKHIN, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1962, **7**, 401 ; Ref. *Zhur. Khim.*, 11, 1962, 21, Abstr. No. 21 D 57.
8. N. H. FURMAN, *Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis*, D. Van Nostrand Company Inc., Princeton, New Jersey, Toronto, New York, London, Vol. 1. The Elements, Sixth Edition, 1966.
9. J. ROSIN, "Reagent Chemicals and Standards", D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., Princeton, New Jersey, Toronto, London, Fifth Edition, 1967.
10. H. T. S. BRITTON, *Hydrogen Ions*, D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., 4th Edition, Vol. 1, 1956.
11. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA and R. M. AWADALLAH, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1975, **18**, No. 2, 211.
12. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA and R. M. AWADALLAH, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1975, **18**, No. 5, 801.